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Review article

The information needs of relatives of childhood cancer patients and survivors: A systematic review of quantitative evidence

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ABSTRACT

Objective: We aimed to: (1) summarize the quantitative evidence on the information needs of relatives of childhood cancer patients, survivors, and children deceased from cancer; and (2) identify factors associated with these needs.**Methods:** PubMed, PsycINFO, Scopus, and CINAHL were systematically searched. The methodological quality of all included publications was assessed, and the extracted data were analyzed using narrative synthesis.**Results:** Of 5810 identified articles, 45 were included. Information needs were classified as unmet, met (satisfied), and unspecified and categorized into five domains: medical information, cancer-related consequences, lifestyle, family, and support. Most unmet information needs concerned cancer-related consequences (e.g., late effects), while information needs on support were generally met. Migrant background and higher education were associated with higher information needs among parents. Siblings had lower information needs than parents.**Conclusion:** This systematic review provides a comprehensive overview of the information needs of relatives in the context of childhood cancer, showing that information on cancer-related consequences is needed most often. The socioeconomic background of the relatives needs continued consideration throughout the cancer trajectory.**Practice implications:** Our findings suggest the need for personalized information. Healthcare professionals should adapt their communication strategies to respond to the different and evolving needs of all affected relatives.

1. Introduction

Every year, approximately 400'000 children aged up to 14 years develop childhood cancer [1]. Global childhood cancer survival rates have increased significantly during the past years following medical advancements [2,3]. Besides the direct impact on the patient, a cancer diagnosis is devastating for the entire family. Relatives cope with an

increased emotional strain and rearrange the family system by changing routines, priorities, and responsibilities [4]. Parents adopt decision-making roles and take action to do what is best for their sick child [5]. Healthy siblings may experience anxiety in the new situation, tend to undertake parental responsibilities, and deal with changes in their social lives [4,6,7]. Grandparents or other extended family members usually provide practical and emotional support [8]. All involved

Abbreviations: ALL, Acute lymphoblastic leukemia; AML, Acute myeloid leukemia; BMT, Bone marrow transplant; CML, Chronic myeloid leukemia; CNS, Central nervous system; eHealth, Electronic health; FIN-PED II, Family Inventory of Needs - Paediatric II; HL, Hodgkin lymphoma; ICC-3, International Classification of Childhood Cancer, Third Edition; NCLE, Neurocognitive late effects; NHL, Non-Hodgkin lymphoma; PNET, Primitive neuroectodermal tumors; SES, Socioeconomic status.

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individuals may experience increased distress, which can affect their quality of life [4–6,9,10]. After a childhood cancer diagnosis, involved individuals may engage in information-seeking to satisfy their needs, such as coping with the disease burden. Patient health information needs are defined as “[...] a recognition that your knowledge is inadequate to satisfy a goal that you have, within the context / situation that you find yourself at a specific point in the time” (p. 99) [11].

Being informed can positively influence relatives’ emotion regulation, decision-making, and symptom management of the ill child [4,12]. Therefore, understanding and meeting the information needs of family members is necessary for optimal health and healthcare outcomes. As these needs are highly personal, identifying them remains challenging [13]. Several studies have analyzed the information needs of relatives of childhood cancer patients and survivors, and relatives of children deceased from cancer. Hereafter, we will refer to these groups collectively as relatives of childhood cancer patients and survivors. However, a complete, structured overview of the quantitative evidence is lacking. Therefore, this systematic review aims to; (1) summarize the quantitative evidence on the information needs of relatives and close friends of childhood cancer patients and survivors; and (2) identify factors associated with these needs.

2. Methods

A protocol including the study objectives and methodology has been registered in the PROSPERO database (registration number: CRD42022382412). The review is reported according to the PRISMA 2020 statement [14].

2.1. Search strategy

A systematic search strategy was developed to obtain peer-reviewed research on the information needs of relatives and close friends of childhood cancer patients and survivors. The databases PubMed, PsycINFO, Scopus, and CINAHL were searched on 25 July 2019, and we ran an update on 19 July 2022 and 23 August 2023. The search terms included four blocks: “childhood”, “cancer”, “family members” and “information needs”, which were adapted to each database (Appendix A). The “humans only” filter was used when possible, and no language restrictions were selected. Reference lists of included articles were hand-searched for additional relevant research.

2.2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

We included only original peer-reviewed articles that quantitatively (including mixed methods) assessed the self-reported information needs of relatives and close friends of childhood cancer patients and survivors or reported factors associated with these needs. To provide a comprehensive overview, we also included research on bereaved relatives, as there was no other review that specifically addressed their information needs. We excluded articles that focused on (1) other diseases or without a clear distinction between childhood cancer and other diseases; (2) without a clear distinction between information needs and other support needs; (3) without a clear distinction between patients’ or survivors’ and relatives’ information needs; (4) languages other than English, German, French, Italian, Spanish, Dutch, Serbo-Croatian, and Romanian (as spoken in the research team); (5) (systematic) reviews and meta-analyses; and (6) articles published before 2007, to focus on recent developments of advanced digital health and communication technologies. Publications applying only qualitative methods and qualitative results of studies using mixed methods were synthesized in a separate review [13].

2.3. Screening and selection

After removing all duplicates, two independent reviewers each (YS, KR or GM, and AI) screened the potentially relevant articles. Excel

(search 1) and the online software Rayyan (search 2 and 3) were used for title and abstract screening, followed by full-text screening for a final decision [15]. Disagreement was solved with discussion or involving a third reviewer.

2.4. Data extraction

We extracted descriptive data on (1) study characteristics (author(s), title, year, country of data collection, study design, method of assessment, area of information needs); (2) population of interest (kinship or relationship with patient or survivor, sample size, gender, age, education, employment, socio-economic status, ethnicity, marital status); (3) childhood cancer patients/survivors (sample size, gender, cancer diagnosis, treatment, disease stage, age); and (4) outcome measures.

The main outcome included self-reported information needs of relatives and close friends of childhood cancer patients and survivors, for which we extracted the following: (1) definition of information needs; (2) identified information needs (name, description, and prevalence); and (3) status of the need at study (met, unmet or unspecified). We classified these three categories based on measurements or definitions as applied in the original articles. Unmet information needs include a desire for (further) information, while met information needs include the fulfillment of desired needs or satisfaction with the amount of information received. Unspecified information needs occur when the article does not report or distinguish if the need is met or unmet. When the article reported multiple levels of information needs (e.g., low/moderate/high), only information on moderate to high needs were extracted, to exclude categories of no or minor needs, and focus on critical needs [16–18]. The secondary outcome included factors associated with information needs, for which we extracted all characteristics associated with higher information needs. Data were extracted using a standardized data extraction table, which was pilot tested on five articles and subsequently refined. Data extraction of the first search was conducted by AI and double-checked by YS, and vice versa for the second and third search. Disagreements have been discussed until a consensus was reached.

2.5. Quality assessment

All articles were subjected to quality assessment according to the 9-item Critical Appraisal Instrument for studies reporting prevalence data developed by the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) [19]. Nine items evaluate the validity of observational studies reporting prevalence estimates, with questions on sampling bias, analysis, and methodology. The tool is recommended due to its face validity, acceptability, and applicability [20,21]. Each item was scored as “yes”, “no”, “unclear”, or “not applicable”, allowing each publication to be categorized as low (0–2 “yes”), moderate (3–6 “yes”), or high (7–9 “yes”) quality. To improve reliability, the first author (YS) conducted the quality assessment, and a second author (AI) independently assessed 20% of the articles. Discordances were discussed, and an agreed strategy to evaluate the remaining articles was established. The quality assessment was conducted to understand the overall quality of the research, and no articles were excluded because of this criterion.

2.6. Synthesis

A narrative synthesis was conducted to describe the prevalence of information needs and investigate the factors associated with higher information needs. We analyzed similarities and differences between studies, investigating associations such as whether needs could be attributed to a specific cancer diagnosis or stage (diagnosis, active treatment, survivorship, bereavement), relationship (parents, siblings, grandparents, close friends), or other characteristics. Information needs were grouped into domains of similar needs. Descriptive statistics were used to describe study characteristics. Percentages and means were

reported to describe prevalence rates (primary outcome). The median for each domain was calculated from the prevalence rates of information needs as reported in the original articles, to allow comparison and give a more accurate representation than the mean due to numerous outliers. For the secondary outcome, significant associations displayed using regression coefficients, correlation values, and odds ratios were reported and interpreted for statistical significance at the 95% confidence level [22].

3. Results

In total, 5810 records were identified, of which 5211 remained after removing duplicates. Title and abstract screening resulted in 208 potentially eligible articles. We retrieved 206 of them and assessed them according to the exclusion criteria. No publication was added via hand-searching reference lists. After the full-text screening, 45 articles were included in the current review (Fig. 1).

3.1. Study characteristics

3.1.1. Design

Most articles used a quantitative methodology ($n = 37$), and eight applied mixed methods. Nearly all studies adopted a cross-sectional study design ($n = 41$), and four applied a longitudinal design (Table 1).

3.1.2. Country

Most of the studies were conducted in North America ($n = 15$), followed by Europe ($n = 11$), Asia ($n = 11$), Oceania ($n = 7$), and Africa ($n = 1$).

3.1.3. Childhood cancer diagnosis

Nearly half of all diagnoses were leukemias, most commonly acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL). Other common diagnoses included retinoblastomas, Wilms tumors, non-Hodgkin lymphomas, and central nervous system (CNS) tumors.

3.1.4. Cancer stage

The articles addressed various stages throughout the cancer

trajectory. Fifteen articles focused on active treatment, 12 on survivorship, and two on bereavement. Fifteen articles included multiple stages and one article did not specify the stage [23].

3.1.5. Participants

Nine articles analyzed both patients or survivors and relatives, but only data concerning the relatives were included in the current review. Most articles focused on primary caregivers ($n = 39$), only six articles included other relatives (siblings $n = 5$, grandparents $n = 3$), and none included close friends. Generally, articles included more female than male participants.

3.1.6. Assessment methods

Most articles measured information needs with a self-developed survey questionnaire based on previous research ($n = 7$) or using an adaptation of existing questionnaires ($n = 10$). Ten articles used validated instruments that measure unmet, met, or unspecified information needs with distinct items for the different need statuses. The Family Inventory of Needs-Paediatrics II (FIN-PED II) was common to measure the importance of care needs, need fulfillment and need for further information ($n = 3$). One article measured information needs by combining three different instruments [24]. Another article developed the assessment tool Sibling Cancer Needs Instrument [18], which was consequently used by other authors [25].

3.2. Quality assessment

The quality assessment of the included publications is presented in Table 2. The initial intercoder agreement was 68.9%. The final assessment of each article showed four articles of low quality, 35 of moderate quality, and six of high quality. They did not differ substantially, but the articles with lower quality lacked clarity. Almost all articles clearly reported an appropriate sample frame, study subjects, and statistical analyses. Information on sample size calculation, non-participants, confidence intervals, and statistical assumptions was rarely provided. This resulted in an overall moderate methodological quality, with a mean score of 4.8 no. of "yes" (SD 1.6, range: 2–8), which was evaluated as moderate.

Fig. 1. PRISMA 2020 flow diagram [14].

Table 1
Study characteristics, ordered by cancer stage at study.

First author, year, country	Title	Area of information needs ^a Status of need	Type of childhood cancer diagnosis	Participants	Assessment method of information needs
Cancer stage at study:^b Active treatment					
Arabiat, 2013, Jordan [26]	Unmet care needs of parents of children with cancer in Jordan: implications for bed-side practice	Not specified Unmet needs, met needs	Leukemia (ALL/AML): <i>n</i> = 50 Solid tumors: <i>n</i> = 47 Not reported: <i>n</i> = 1	<i>n</i> = 98 parents (<i>n</i> = 79 mothers, <i>n</i> = 19 fathers)	Family Inventory of Needs - Paediatric II (FIN-PED II) – Arabic translation Importance of care needs Extent to which information needs are met Need for further information Self-developed 10 items: nutritional information needs of parents
Arpaci, 2018, Turkey [27]	Assessment of nutritional problems in pediatric patients with cancer and the information needs of their parents: A parental perspective	Nutrition Met needs, unspecified needs	Leukemia: <i>n</i> = 31 Solid tumor: <i>n</i> = 18 CNS: <i>n</i> = 11 Lymphoma: <i>n</i> = 8 Other: <i>n</i> = 1	<i>n</i> = 69 parents (<i>n</i> = 59 mothers ^c)	Self-developed based on previous surveys and new literature Parent information preferences about possible future limitations Parent perceptions of information quality Adaptation of Information Styles Questionnaire and Information Needs Questionnaire Information preferences about diagnosis, treatment and likelihood of cure Self-developed What items they wished members of the oncology care team had discussed more or given more information about
Greenzang, 2018, USA [28]	Parent understanding of the risk of future limitations secondary to pediatric cancer treatment	Risks of potential long-term effects Unspecified needs	Hematologic malignancies: <i>n</i> = 173 Solid tumor: <i>n</i> = 136 CNS: <i>n</i> = 43	<i>n</i> = 352 parents (<i>n</i> = 281 mothers, <i>n</i> = 68 fathers)	Self-developed based on previous surveys and new literature Parent information preferences about possible future limitations Parent perceptions of information quality Adaptation of Information Styles Questionnaire and Information Needs Questionnaire Information preferences about diagnosis, treatment and likelihood of cure Self-developed What items they wished members of the oncology care team had discussed more or given more information about
Ilowite, 2017, USA [29]	Disparities in prognosis communication among parents of children with cancer: The impact of race and ethnicity	Prognosis communication Unspecified needs	Hematologic malignancies: <i>n</i> = 176 Solid tumor: <i>n</i> = 138 CNS: <i>n</i> = 43	<i>n</i> = 357 parents (<i>n</i> = 289 mothers, <i>n</i> = 68 fathers)	Self-developed based on standardized measurement tool Information needs Self-developed based on previous studies 7 items: illness-related information received and preferences
Levine, 2019, USA [30]	Are we meeting the informational needs of cancer patients and families? Perception of physician communication in pediatric oncology	Not specified Unmet needs, met needs	CNS: <i>n</i> = 20 Leukemia: <i>n</i> = 38 Lymphoma: <i>n</i> = 26 Solid tumor: <i>n</i> = 41 Other: <i>n</i> = 1 Unknown: <i>n</i> = 3	<i>n</i> = 129 parents (<i>n</i> = 114 mothers, <i>n</i> = 15 fathers)	Self-developed based on standardized measurement tool Information needs Self-developed based on previous studies 7 items: illness-related information received and preferences
Lewandowska, 2022, Poland [11]	The needs of parents of children suffering from cancer—continuation of research	Not specified Unmet needs	Leukemia: <i>n</i> = 432 CNS: <i>n</i> = 152 Solid tumors: <i>n</i> = 216	<i>n</i> = 800 parents (<i>n</i> = 680 mothers, <i>n</i> = 120 fathers)	Self-developed based on standardized measurement tool Information needs Self-developed based on previous studies 7 items: illness-related information received and preferences
Lövgren, 2020, Sweden [31]	Much is left unspeaken: Self-reports from families in pediatric oncology	Illness-related information Unmet needs, met needs	CNS: <i>n</i> = 13 Leukemia: <i>n</i> = 5 Lymphoma: <i>n</i> = 5 Sarcoma: <i>n</i> = 2 Other: <i>n</i> = 2	<i>n</i> = 53 parents (<i>n</i> = 29 mothers, <i>n</i> = 24 fathers) <i>n</i> = 38 siblings (<i>n</i> = 20 sisters, <i>n</i> = 18 brothers)	Self-developed based on previous studies 3 items: Medical information 3 items: Physical care information 4 items: Mental care information 3 items: Lifestyle information Adaptation of Comprehensive Satisfaction with Care, Short Form, Version 4.0 (CASC SF) Satisfaction with child's care Information provision Need Opportunity Benefit to talk to others Self-developed based on previous surveys Information needs preferences for formatting and content Survey of Unmet Support Needs of the Support Person, short version (SPUNS) Information needs PedsQL (quality of life)
Masoudifar, 2022, Iran [25]	Unfulfilled psychosocial needs of the adolescent siblings of patients with cancer and the identification of the related factors	Not specified Unmet needs	Leukemia: <i>n</i> = 111 Lymphoma: <i>n</i> = 15 Musculoskeletal: <i>n</i> = 17 Neural: <i>n</i> = 13 Other: <i>n</i> = 24	<i>n</i> = 180 siblings (<i>n</i> = 98 sisters, <i>n</i> = 82 brothers)	Sibling Cancer Needs Instrument (SCNI) 8 items: information about my sibling's cancer
Motlagh, 2019, Iran [32]	Information needs assessment among parents of children with cancer	Medical information, physical care information, mental care information, lifestyle information Met needs	Leukemia	<i>n</i> = 187 parents (<i>n</i> = 125 mothers, <i>n</i> = 62 fathers)	Self-developed based on previous studies 3 items: Medical information 3 items: Physical care information 4 items: Mental care information 3 items: Lifestyle information Adaptation of Comprehensive Satisfaction with Care, Short Form, Version 4.0 (CASC SF) Satisfaction with child's care Information provision Need Opportunity Benefit to talk to others Self-developed based on previous surveys Information needs preferences for formatting and content Survey of Unmet Support Needs of the Support Person, short version (SPUNS) Information needs PedsQL (quality of life)
Pöder, 2009, Sweden [33]	Perceptions of support among Swedish parents of children on cancer treatment: A prospective, longitudinal study	Disease, medical tests, care and treatment Met needs	Leukemia: <i>n</i> = 50 CNS: <i>n</i> = 14 Other solid tumors: <i>n</i> = 51	<i>n</i> = 214 parents (<i>n</i> = 107 mothers, <i>n</i> = 107 fathers)	Self-developed based on previous studies 3 items: Medical information 3 items: Physical care information 4 items: Mental care information 3 items: Lifestyle information Adaptation of Comprehensive Satisfaction with Care, Short Form, Version 4.0 (CASC SF) Satisfaction with child's care Information provision Need Opportunity Benefit to talk to others Self-developed based on previous surveys Information needs preferences for formatting and content Survey of Unmet Support Needs of the Support Person, short version (SPUNS) Information needs PedsQL (quality of life)
Robinson, 2019, USA [34]	The many roles of the rock: A qualitative inquiry into the roles and responsibilities of fathers of children with brain tumors	Brain tumors Unspecified needs	CNS	<i>n</i> = 4 fathers	Self-developed based on previous surveys Information needs preferences for formatting and content Survey of Unmet Support Needs of the Support Person, short version (SPUNS) Information needs PedsQL (quality of life)
Rosado, 2021, Mexico [35]	Need of psychological support and assessment of quality of life of family caregivers of children with cancer	Not specified Unmet needs	Leukemia: <i>n</i> = 48 ^c Lymphomas: <i>n</i> = 13 ^c Bone tumors: <i>n</i> = 10 ^c CNS: <i>n</i> = 5 ^c Other: <i>n</i> = 24 ^c	<i>n</i> = 97 parents (<i>n</i> = 91 mothers, <i>n</i> = 6 fathers) <i>n</i> = 2 grandmothers <i>n</i> = 1 sister	Self-developed based on previous surveys Information needs preferences for formatting and content Survey of Unmet Support Needs of the Support Person, short version (SPUNS) Information needs PedsQL (quality of life)

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Table 1 (continued)

First author, year, country	Title	Area of information needs ^a Status of need	Type of childhood cancer diagnosis	Participants	Assessment method of information needs
Terrasson, 2023, France [36]	The announcement of treatment resistance in pediatric oncology: Understanding parents' experiences and influencing factors with a mixed methodology	Not specified Unmet needs, met needs	High-risk brain tumor: <i>n</i> = 4 High-risk sarcoma: <i>n</i> = 1 Hepatoblastoma: <i>n</i> = 1 Nephroblastoma: <i>n</i> = 1 Choroid plexus carcinoma: <i>n</i> = 1	<i>n</i> = 15 parents (<i>n</i> = 8 mothers, <i>n</i> = 7 fathers)	European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer's Quality of Life Questionnaire - Information Module (EORTC QLQ-INFO25) Perception of the information received about the disease, medical tests and treatments Overall satisfaction with the medical information received Prognosis and Treatment Perception Questionnaire (PTPQ) Parents' perceptions of their child's disease prognosis and treatment
Wakefield, 2014, Australia [16]	'What they're not telling you': a new scale to measure grandparents' information needs when their grandchild has cancer	Not specified Unmet needs	Leukemia: <i>n</i> = 35 Lymphoma: <i>n</i> = 4 Solid tumors: <i>n</i> = 28 Other: <i>n</i> = 14	<i>n</i> = 87 grandparents (<i>n</i> = 57 grandmothers, <i>n</i> = 27 grandfathers)	Adaptation of Patient Information Needs Questionnaire (PINQ; 15 items) Grandparents' need for information regarding topics related to their grandchild's cancer
Wang, 2022, China [37]	The relationship between the unmet needs of Chinese family caregivers and the quality of life of childhood cancer patients undergoing inpatient treatment: A mediation model through caregiver depression	Treatment, dietary, home care, communication skills, and stress management Unmet needs	Leukemia: <i>n</i> = 150 Solid Tumor: <i>n</i> = 136	<i>n</i> = 286 caregivers (<i>n</i> = 203 females, <i>n</i> = 83 males)	Comprehensive Needs Assessment Tool for Cancer Caregivers (CNAT-C)
Cancer stage at study:^b Survivorship					
Aukema, 2011, Netherlands [38]	Explorative study on the aftercare of pediatric brain tumor survivors: A parents' perspective	Aftercare Unmet needs	CNS: Infratentorial: <i>n</i> = 26 Supratentorial: <i>n</i> = 16 High grade: <i>n</i> = 19 Low grade: <i>n</i> = 23 CNS: <i>n</i> = 25 Medulloblastoma Optic pathway glioma Pilocytic astrocytoma Childhood cancer: <i>n</i> = 22 ALL NHL/HL Solid tumors	<i>n</i> = 42 parents (<i>n</i> = 34 mothers, <i>n</i> = 8 fathers)	Self-developed Need for aftercare Needs for improvements
Hauff, 2019 USA [39]	Adolescent survivors' information needs for transitions to postsecondary education and employment	Transition to postsecondary education, employment and adulthood Unmet needs	CNS: <i>n</i> = 25 Medulloblastoma Optic pathway glioma Pilocytic astrocytoma Childhood cancer: <i>n</i> = 22 ALL NHL/HL Solid tumors	<i>n</i> = 47 parents	Self-developed 9 items: Education and training 10 items: Transition planning
Hobbie, 2010, USA [40]	Identifying the educational needs of parents at the completion of their child's cancer therapy	Late effects Unspecified needs	ALL: <i>n</i> = 6 AML: <i>n</i> = 1 Ewing sarcoma: <i>n</i> = 2 Rhabdomyosarcoma: <i>n</i> = 2 Brain tumor: <i>n</i> = 1 Lymphoblastic lymphoma: <i>n</i> = 1 Osteosarcoma: <i>n</i> = 1 Not reported: <i>n</i> = 1 Astrocytoma: <i>n</i> = 252 Ependymoma: <i>n</i> = 52 Medulloblastoma/PNET: <i>n</i> = 68 Other CNS: <i>n</i> = 179 Solid tumor: <i>n</i> = 272 Hematologic malignancy: <i>n</i> = 222 Leukemia: <i>n</i> = 72 ^c	<i>n</i> = 15 parents	Adaptation of coming off-therapy (COT) needs survey Families' information needs at therapy completion Ideal circumstances and timing for delivery of this information
Hovén, 2018, Sweden [17]	Information needs of survivors and families after childhood CNS tumor treatment: a population-based study	CNS cancer Unmet needs, met needs	Astrocytoma: <i>n</i> = 252 Ependymoma: <i>n</i> = 52 Medulloblastoma/PNET: <i>n</i> = 68 Other CNS: <i>n</i> = 179 Solid tumor: <i>n</i> = 272 Hematologic malignancy: <i>n</i> = 222 Leukemia: <i>n</i> = 72 ^c	<i>n</i> = 551 parents	Self-developed based on the QLQ-INFO26 inventory Information needs Satisfaction with the quality and amount of the information
Jeon, 2022, Korea [41]	Factors associated with the comprehensive needs of caregivers of childhood cancer survivors in Korea	Not specified Unmet needs	Solid tumor: <i>n</i> = 272 Hematologic malignancy: <i>n</i> = 222 Leukemia: <i>n</i> = 72 ^c	<i>n</i> = 700 parents (<i>n</i> = 437 mothers, <i>n</i> = 263 fathers)	Comprehensive Needs Assessment Tool for Cancer Caregivers (CNAT-C) 8 items: information needs; how much help is needed for each care issue
Nicklin, 2022, UK [42]	Long-term unmet supportive care needs of teenage and young adult (TYA) childhood brain tumour survivors and their caregivers: A cross-sectional survey	Not specified Unmet needs	CNS Medulloblastoma: <i>n</i> = 16 Astrocytoma: <i>n</i> = 11 Craniopharyngioma: <i>n</i> = 1 Pineal tumor: <i>n</i> = 1 Choroid plexus carcinoma: <i>n</i> = 2 Ependymoma: <i>n</i> = 3 Other: <i>n</i> = 9	<i>n</i> = 43 parents (<i>n</i> = 37 mothers, <i>n</i> = 6 fathers)	Supportive Care Needs Survey for Partners & Caregivers (SCNS-P&C). 7 items: information needs

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Table 1 (continued)

First author, year, country	Title	Area of information needs ^a Status of need	Type of childhood cancer diagnosis	Participants	Assessment method of information needs
Rao, 2022, India [43]	Inception of a pediatric cancer caregiver support group guided by parental needs	Support groups Unmet needs	Not reported	n = 16 parents (n = 9 mothers, n = 7 fathers) n = 1 uncle	Self-developed based on literature and National Comprehensive Cancer Network Distress Thermometer (NCCN) Informational concerns Level of importance Need for professional assistance Self-developed (based on Ruble [61])
Thornton, 2022, USA [44]	Addressing schooling in children with cancer—It's everybody's job, so it's nobody's job: An explanatory mixed-methods evaluation	Neurocognitive effects from therapy Unmet needs, met needs	ALL: 43.5% Lymphoma: 15.5% CNS: 13.7% AML: 7.7% Other non-CNS: 19.6%	n = 174 parents (n = 78 mothers, n = 96 fathers)	Self-developed (based on Ruble [61])
Vetsch, 2015, Switzerland [45]	Information needs in parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors	Illness, treatment, follow-up and late effects Unmet needs, met needs	Leukemia: n = 74 CNS: n = 34 Lymphomas: n = 16 Soft tissue sarcomas: n = 14 Neuroblastoma: n = 13 Retinoblastoma: n = 13 Renal tumors: n = 12 Hepatic tumors: n = 4 Malignant tumors: n = 2 Germ cell tumors: n = 2 Langerhans cell histiocytosis: n = 2 Other: n = 3	n = 189 parents (n = 160 mothers, n = 29 fathers)	Self-developed Perceptions about having received information Current information needs Preferred format for information
Vetsch, 2017, Australia [46]	Forewarned and forearmed: Long-term childhood cancer survivors' and parents' information needs and implications for survivorship models of care	Medical topics, psychosocial needs and lifestyle behaviors Met needs, unspecified needs	Leukemia: n = 76 Lymphoma: n = 14 CNS: n = 7 Other: n = 65	n = 163 parents (n = 137 mothers, n = 23 fathers)	Self-developed (22 items) Medical topics Psychosocial needs Lifestyle behaviors
Vetsch, 2020, Australia, New Zealand [47]	Genetics-related service and information needs of childhood cancer survivors and parents: A mixed-methods study	Genetics-related services Unmet needs, unspecified needs	Leukemia: n = 97 Lymphoma: n = 16 Solid tumor: n = 80 Other: n = 10 Not reported: n = 15	n = 218 parents (n = 175 mothers, n = 27 fathers)	Self-developed 1 item: genetics-related information needs 2 items: information need about risks to other family members and survivors' future children Self-developed (7 items) How sources would meet their needs
Wakefield, 2012, Australia [48]	Family information needs at childhood cancer treatment completion	Transition after treatment Unmet needs	Not reported	n = 78 parents (n = 44 mothers, n = 34 fathers) n = 15 siblings	Self-developed (7 items) How sources would meet their needs
Cancer stage at study:^b Multiple stages					
Al-Dhawani, 2022, Oman [49]	Factors contributing to the unmet needs of primary Cregivers of Omani children diagnosed with eukemia	Not specified Met needs	ALL: n = 77 AML: n = 20 Mixed: n = 2 Other: n = 2	n = 101 parents (n = 89 mothers, n = 12 fathers)	Needs Assessment of Family Caregivers-Cancer (NAFC-C) – Arabic version 10 items: obtaining information Perceived degree of importance Level of satisfaction
Aziza, 2019, Indonesia [50]	Unmet supportive care needs and psychological distress among parents of children with cancer in Indonesia	Not specified Unmet needs	ALL: n = 39 AML: n = 11 NHL/HL: n = 16 Osteosarcoma: n = 8 Rhabdomyosarcoma: n = 3 Other: n = 23	n = 100 parents (n = 73 mothers, n = 27 fathers)	Adaptation of Supportive Care Needs Survey Partners and Caregivers (SCNS P&C) – Indonesian translation 7 items: informational needs
Christiansen, 2008, UK [51]	Oral chemotherapy in paediatric oncology in the UK: problems, perceptions and information needs of parents	Oral chemotherapy Unmet needs, met needs, unspecified needs	ALL	n = 55 parents (n = 46 mothers)	Self-developed Desired information Used sources
Gunawan, 2014, Indonesia [52]	Parents' and health-care providers' perspectives on side-effects of childhood cancer treatment in Indonesia	Chemotherapy-related side-effects Unmet needs, met needs	Hematologic tumors: n = 36 ^c ALL: n = 31 ^c Solid tumors: n = 4 ^c	n = 37 parents (n = 32 mothers, n = 5 fathers) ^c	Self-developed Perspectives on chemotherapy-related side effects of treatment
Jacobson, 2020, USA [53]	Barriers to schooling in survivorship: The role of neuropsychological assessment	Neuropsychological assessment/services and schooling Unmet needs	CNS: n = 71 ALL: n = 84 AML: n = 14 Lymphoma: n = 27 Other non-CNS: n = 38 Wilms tumor: n = 8 Ewing sarcoma: n = 6 Rhabdomyosarcoma: n = 6 Osteosarcoma: n = 4 Retinoblastoma: n = 3	n = 195 parents (n = 179 mothers, n = 12 fathers) ^c	Self-developed Perceived barriers to school reentry and/or obtaining supports for their children after diagnosis Utility of the neuropsychological evaluation and the written report

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

First author, year, country	Title	Area of information needs ^a Status of need	Type of childhood cancer diagnosis	Participants	Assessment method of information needs
Karst, 2018, USA [54]	Assessment of end-of-treatment transition needs for pediatric cancer and hematopoietic stem cell transplant patients and their families	Transition at end of treatment Unmet needs, unspecified needs	Neuroblastoma: n = 2 Other: n = 8 Leukemia: n = 23 Bone/soft tissue: n = 11 Lymphoma: n = 8 Hematology (BMT): n = 4 CNS: n = 2 Solid tumor: n = 1	n = 49 parents (n = 37 mothers, n = 10 fathers)	Self-developed: What information would be helpful at end of treatment (T1) If this information was provided (T2)
Kerr, 2007, Canada [55]	Understanding the supportive care needs of parents of children with cancer: An approach to local needs assessment	Not specified Unmet needs	Leukemia/Lymphoma: n = 6 ^c Rhabdomyosarcoma: n = 2 ^c Hepatoblastoma: n = 2 ^c Primitive neuroectodermal tumor: n = 2 ^c Not reported: n = 3 ^c ALL	n = 15 parents (n = 14 mothers)	Adaptation of SNCF and Cancer Patient Needs Questionnaire (CPNQ) 9 items: informational needs
Liu, 2023, China [56]	The demands of caregivers of children with acute lymphoblastic leukaemia in different therapy stages and the exploration of possible interventions: A longitudinal investigation survey at a Tertiary Medical Institution	Not specified Unmet needs	ALL	n = 142 parents (n = 100 mothers, n = 42 fathers) n = 9 grandparents (n = 6 grandmothers, n = 3 grandfathers)	Adaptation of the Comprehensive Needs of Caregivers of Cancer Patients and Families Taking Care of Children Scale 8 items: information demands
McKenna, 2010, UK [57]	Parental involvement in paediatric cancer treatment decisions	Not specified Unmet needs	ALL: n = 29 Wilms tumor: n = 6 AML: n = 3 NHL: n = 3 Other: n = 25	n = 66 parents (n = 50 mothers, n = 16 fathers)	Self-developed: 1 item: satisfaction with involvement in the child's treatment decision 1 item: desired additional information about treatment options
Moody, 2011, USA [58]	Psychosocial needs of ethnic minority, inner-city, pediatric cancer patients	Cancer, treatment, symptom management and lifestyle change Unmet needs	ALL: n = 39 CNS: n = 16 Sarcoma: n = 15 Lymphoma: n = 9 Neuroblastoma: n = 9 HL: n = 6 AML: n = 4 Aplastic anemia: n = 3 Other: n = 2	n = 91 parents (n = 21 fathers)	Adaptation of Psychosocial Needs Assessment Survey 16 items: informational needs
Njuguna, 2015, Kenya [59]	Parental experiences of childhood cancer treatment in Kenya	Not specified Unmet needs, met needs	ALL: n = 23 NHL: n = 16 Nephroblastoma: n = 12 HL: n = 5 CML: n = 3 Germ Cell tumor: n = 3 Neuroblastoma: n = 3 Retinoblastoma: n = 3 Rhabdomyosarcoma: n = 2 Osteosarcoma: n = 2 AML: n = 2 Kaposi Sarcoma: n = 1	n = 75 parents (n = 70 mothers, n = 15 fathers) ^c	Self-developed Treatment-related and psychological experiences during treatment
Oosterhuis, 2008, USA [60]	Concerns about infertility risks among pediatric oncology patients and their parents	Infertility risks Met needs	Leukemia: n = 51 Lymphoma: n = 23 CNS: n = 5 Other: n = 18 Hepatoblastoma Neuroblastoma Rhabdomyosarcoma Osteosarcoma Wilms tumor	n = 97 parents	Self-developed (15 items) Concerns about fertility-related side effects of cancer treatment Satisfaction with information about possible treatment effects on fertility Information desired for the future
Patterson, 2011, Australia [18]	The development of an instrument to assess the unmet needs of young people who have a sibling with cancer: piloting the Sibling Cancer Needs Instrument (SCNI)	Cancer, treatment, side effects, alter-natives, rehabilitation, recovery statistics Unspecified needs	Leukemia: n = 35 Bone tumor: n = 9 NHL: n = 7 Brain: n = 7 HL: n = 7 Other: n = 5 Not reported: n = 1	n = 71 siblings (n = 45 sisters, n = 26 brothers)	Self-developed Sibling Cancer Needs Instrument (SCNI) 6 items: need for information and whether or not they are met
Ruble, 2019, USA [61]	Parent perspectives on oncology team communication regarding neurocognitive impacts of cancer therapy and school reentry	Neurocognitive impacts and school reentry Unmet needs	ALL: n = 91 ^c Lymphoma: n = 32 ^c NHL: n = 16 ^c CNS: n = 27 ^c Ependymoma: n = 6 ^c Medulloblastoma: n = 5 ^c	n = 203 parents (n = 188 mothers)	Self-developed Timing Utility Topics of information

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Table 1 (continued)

First author, year, country	Title	Area of information needs ^a Status of need	Type of childhood cancer diagnosis	Participants	Assessment method of information needs
Trask, 2009, USA [62]	Parental needs for information related to neurocognitive late effects from pediatric cancer and its treatment	Neurocognitive late effects Unmet needs	Pilocytic astrocytoma: <i>n</i> = 5 ^c Other astrocytoma: <i>n</i> = 3 ^c Other: <i>n</i> = 7 ^c AML: <i>n</i> = 37 ^c Other non-CNS: <i>n</i> = 37 ^c Wilms tumor: <i>n</i> = 8 ^c Ewing sarcoma: <i>n</i> = 6 ^c Rhabdomyosarcoma: <i>n</i> = 6 ^c Osteosarcoma: <i>n</i> = 5 ^c Retinoblastoma: <i>n</i> = 3 ^c Other: <i>n</i> = 49 ^c ALL: <i>n</i> = 66 ^c CNS: <i>n</i> = 20 ^c NHL: <i>n</i> = 4 ^c	<i>n</i> = 90 parents	Adaptation of previous tools (Bar-Tal, Barnoy, and Zisser's measure; Peds QL Healthcare Satisfaction Hematology/Oncology module)
Cancer stage at study:^b Bereavement					
Bronsema, 2022 Germany [63]	Looking back: Identifying supportive care and unmet needs of parents of children receiving specialist paediatric palliative care from the bereavement perspective	Not specified Unmet needs, met needs	Leukemia: <i>n</i> = 3 CNS: <i>n</i> = 9 Solid tumor: <i>n</i> = 6	<i>n</i> = 18 parents (<i>n</i> = 10 mothers, <i>n</i> = 8 fathers)	Family Inventory of Needs - Paediatric II (FIN-PED II; 17 items) Importance of care needs Need fulfilment Further information
Monterosso, 2009, Australia [24]	The supportive and palliative care needs of Australian families of children who die from cancer	Palliative and supportive care needs Unmet needs, met needs	Neuroblastoma: <i>n</i> = 11 CNS Other: <i>n</i> = 11 Medulloblastoma: <i>n</i> = 8 Astrocytoma: <i>n</i> = 5 Rhabdomyosarcoma: <i>n</i> = 4 ALL: <i>n</i> = 7 Other: <i>n</i> = 7 Sarcoma Undifferentiated: <i>n</i> = 3 Soft tissue: <i>n</i> = 2 Osteogenic: <i>n</i> = 2 Ewing's/PNET: <i>n</i> = 2 AML: <i>n</i> = 2 NHL: <i>n</i> = 2 Retinoblastoma: <i>n</i> = 2 Hepatoblastoma: <i>n</i> = 1	<i>n</i> = 69 parents	Service and Educational Resource Utilisation (SERU; 13 items) Carer needs importance related to services and educational resources Need fulfilment Further information required Patient Carer's Needs Survey (PCNS) from Home Caregiver Needs Survey (16 items) Parents' perceived importance of a need Need fulfilment If they would have liked more information Family Inventory of Needs - Paediatric II (FIN-PED II; 17 items) Importance of care needs Need fulfilment Need for more information
Cancer stage at study:^b Not specified					
Thomas, 2023, Australia [23]	Unmet supportive care needs in families of children with chronic health conditions: an Australian cross-sectional study	Not specified Unmet needs	Not reported	<i>n</i> = 39 parents (<i>n</i> = 38 mothers, <i>n</i> = 1 father)	Adaptation of Family Inventory of Needs-Pediatric II (FIN-PED II) and Cancer Survivors Unmet Needs scale (CaSUN) 4 items: informational needs

⁴ The article reported numbers inconsistently throughout

Abbreviations: ALL, Acute lymphoblastic leukemia; AML, Acute myeloid leukemia; BMT, Bone marrow transplant; CML, Chronic myeloid leukemia; CNS, Central nervous system; NHL, Non-Hodgkin lymphoma; HL, Hodgkin lymphoma; PNET, Primitive neuroectodermal tumors

^a Studies may focus on information needs in a specific area or report on information needs in general without restricting to one area.

^b Some studies assess information needs retrospectively and may cause discrepancy between the timing along the cancer continuum and the children's disease stage at the time of the study

^c The number was calculated from percentages in the corresponding article

3.3. Aim 1: prevalence of information needs

Information needs were classified into 5 domains: (1) medical information (i.e., disease and treatment characteristics); (2) cancer-related consequences (i.e., consequences of cancer that a child deals with); (3) lifestyle (i.e., continuation of aspects of a child's regular life apart from cancer); (4) family (i.e., issues of family members); and (5) support (i.e., available services and support). Articles mostly reported medical information needs (discussed in 64% of the articles, *n* = 29). The other needs were mentioned in 49% (*n* = 22), 36% (*n* = 16), 33% (*n* = 15), and 40% (*n* = 18) of the articles, respectively. Table 3 provides an

overview of the studies included in each domain by status of need, and Appendix B summarizes the prevalence rates of all types of information needs by status of need. Fig. 2 provides a visual comparison of the median prevalence rates of met, unmet, and unspecified information needs within the five identified domains.

3.3.1. Unmet information needs

Unmet information needs were identified in all articles (*n* = 45), of which 32 specified a domain. The prevalence of unmet information needs was highest in the domain of cancer-related consequences and lowest in the support domain. Most articles identified a prevalence of

Table 2

Quality assessment of the included articles according to JBI Critical Appraisal Instrument for studies reporting prevalence data (M=4.8 “yes”, SD=1.6).

First author, year	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	No. yes
Al-Dhawyani, 2022 [49]	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	4
Arabiat, 2013 [26]	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	8
Arpaci, 2018 [27]	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	No	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	5
Aukema, 2011 [38]	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Unclear	Yes	Yes	5
Aziza, 2019 [50]	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Yes	5
Bronsema, 2022 [63]	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	6
Hauff, 2019 [39]	Yes	No	Unclear	No	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	2
Christiansen, 2008 [51]	Yes	No	No	No	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	No	3
Greenzang, 2018 [28]	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	6
Gunawan, 2014 [52]	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	6
Hobbie, 2010 [40]	No	No	No	No	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	No	Yes	2
Hovén, 2018 [17]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Yes	7
Ilowite, 2017 [29]	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	5
Jacobson, 2020 [53]	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Unclear	5
Jeon, 2022 [41]	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	6
Karst, 2018 [54]	Yes	Unclear	No	Yes	Yes	No	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	4
Kerr, 2007 [55]	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	6
Levine, 2019 [30]	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	5
Lewandowska, 2022 [11]	No	No	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	No	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	2
Liu, 2023 [56]	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	6
Lövgren, 2020 [31]	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Unclear	Unclear	No	3
Masoudifar, 2022 [25]	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	No	Yes	Unclear	5
McKenna, 2010 [57]	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	No	No	Unclear	Yes	Yes	4
Monterosso, 2009 [24]	No	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	No	3
Moody, 2011 [58]	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	7
Motlagh, 2019 [32]	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	4
Nicklin, 2022 [42]	Yes	Unclear	No	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	4
Njuguna, 2015 [59]	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	No	Yes	Yes	5
Oosterhuis, 2008 [60]	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	8
Patterson, 2011 [18]	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Unclear	No	5
Pöder, 2009 [33]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	5
Rao, 2022 [43]	No	No	No	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Unclear	3
Robinson, 2019 [34]	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Unclear	Yes	4
Rosado, 2021 [35]	Yes	No	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	4
Ruble, 2019 [61]	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	No	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	4
Terrasson, 2023 [36]	Yes	Unclear	No	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	No	2
Thomas, 2023 [23]	Yes	No	Unclear	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	5
Thornton, 2022 [44]	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Unclear	4
Trask, 2009 [62]	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	No	No	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	3
Vetsch, 2015 [45]	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Yes	5
Vetsch, 2017 [46]	Yes	Unclear	Yes	8						
Vetsch, 2020 [47]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	6
Wakefield, 2012 [48]	Unclear	Yes	No	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Yes	No	4
Wakefield, 2014 [16]	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	5
Wang, 2022 [37]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	8

Note:

- 1) Was the sample frame appropriate to address the target population?
- 2) Were study participants sampled in an appropriate way?
- 3) Was the sample size adequate?
- 4) Were the study subjects and the setting described in detail?
- 5) Was the data analysis conducted with sufficient coverage of the identified sample?
- 6) Were valid methods used for the identification of the condition?
- 7) Was the condition measured in a standard, reliable way for all participants?
- 8) Was there appropriate statistical analysis?
- 9) Was the response rate adequate, and if not, was the low response rate managed appropriately?

50% to 87% for specific unmet information needs [23,25,36]. Single studies showed that siblings had fewer unmet information needs than primary caregivers [48], and that unmet information needs decrease with time [54].

Medical information. The prevalence of unmet medical information needs ranged from 0 to 100% and was reported in most articles ($n = 24$) [11,16,17,23–26,30,31,36,42,43,45–48,51,54–59,63]. In this domain, unmet information needs about the child’s health status and illness were highest [11,59]. Unmet information needs on cancer treatments were frequently reported, but the range of prevalence rates was very broad [11,16,17,31,36,45,46,54,55]. This inconsistency was also common for prognosis-related information needs, with the reported prevalence

ranging from 2% to 93% [26,57]. Parents’ unmet need for information on cancer treatments decreased with time [54]. Articles only reported needs on genetics-related information among parents [36,47,58]. Unmet information needs about the cause of illness, rare cancers, and symptoms of recurrence were rare among all participants [17,48].

Cancer-related consequences. The prevalence of unmet information needs in the cancer-related consequences domain was analyzed by 20 articles and was as high as 98%; it mostly included unmet information needs on late effects [17,45,46,54,58]. Three articles reported that family members showed high unmet information needs on side effects of treatment [26,52,58], while two articles reported a comparatively lower level of need regarding this aspect [42,63]. Unmet information needs on

Table 3
Studies on information needs.

Domain of need	Unmet needs	Met needs	Unspecified needs
Medical information	[11,16,17,23–26,30,31,36,42,43,45–48,51,54–59,63]	[17,26,31,32,36,45,49,52,59,63]	[29,34,46,47,51,54]
Cancer-related consequences	[16,17,24,26,30,31,35,38,42–46,48,52,54,58,61–63]	[17,26,30,31,36,44,45,52,63]	[28,46,54]
Lifestyle	[16,17,30,39,42,43,46–48,54,58,61,63]	[27,32,60,63]	[27,46,54]
Family	[16,23,24,26,30,38,42,46,48,51,54–56,63]	[17,24,26,51,63]	[46,54]
Support	[16,17,23,24,26,30,31,36,42,46,53–55,58,61,63]	[17,26,31,32,63]	[34,46,54]

Note: Classification of information needs as reported in the original articles.

post-cancer fatigue were low among parents and siblings [48].

Lifestyle. Thirteen articles reported on unmet information needs in the lifestyle domain. The highest prevalence rate concerned healthy eating (88%) [58]. Other frequent unmet information needs concerned relaxation techniques and learning difficulties [58,61]. In contrast, relatives did not report high unmet information needs on topics such as employment, school, and religious issues [17,30,54].

Family. Unmet information needs in the family domain were studied in 14 articles. Concerning family-related information needs, studies showed many contrasting results. For instance, the need for information on how to care for the sick child at home was reported as unmet for 89% of participants in one study [26], but other articles reported only one third of parents needed more information in this area [23,55,56,63].

Support. Unmet information needs about support were analyzed by 18 articles and were low in general. The highest unmet information needs were reported by up to 89% of participants and concerned asking questions [26]. Unmet information needs on support services were reported by around 50% of parents and siblings [31,42,46].

3.3.2. *Met information needs*

There was less evidence on met information needs and their extent ($n = 16$). Generally, met information needs were most prominent in the domains of medical information and cancer-related consequences [17, 26,30–32,36,44,45,49,52,59,63], and the prevalence went up to 100% [44]. Low rates were found for information needs on fertility and

psychological support, underscoring the importance of addressing these specific areas to address relatives' needs [17,60].

Medical information. Ten articles reported met needs in the domain of medical information. Met information needs in this domain included high prevalence rates for changes in the child's condition and treatment [26,63]. The met need for information about general cancer treatment varied between articles and between different groups of relatives [17, 26,31,45,63]. Prognosis-related information needs were met for most parents, but not for siblings [26,31,36,63].

Cancer-related consequences. Nine articles analyzed cancer-related met information needs. Met information needs were highest for neurocognitive late effects [44]. Met needs on follow-up care, general late effects and side effects showed mixed prevalence rates [17,26, 45,63].

Lifestyle. Only four met information needs were identified in the lifestyle domain, reported in a total of four articles. Information needs related to nutrition, social, and legal issues were mostly met, while information needs related to fertility were met only to a small degree (10%) [27,60].

Family. The extent of met information needs in the family domain was limited ($n = 5$), but a frequently met need was reported for caring for the child at home [17,24,26,63]. For instance, parents indicated that they were well informed on how to administer oral chemotherapy [51].

Support. Although the number of articles investigating met information needs in the support domain was low ($n = 5$), several needs were identified that were mostly met among parents. For example, between 81% and 86% of parents indicated satisfaction with the ability to ask questions at any time, explanations given in understandable terms, and sincerity of healthcare professionals [26,63]. Information about psychological support and help outside the hospital were least fulfilled [17].

3.3.3. *Unspecified information needs*

Unspecified information needs were less commonly reported ($n = 9$), with lifestyle being the most frequently mentioned domain [27,46,54]. The prevalence of unspecified information needs ranged from 16% to 100% [46,54].

Medical information. Six articles analyzed the medical information needs. The prevalence of information needs in the medical domain ranged from 50% to 93% [29,46], except for a low prevalence of 22% for pain-related information [46].

Cancer-related consequences. Only a small number of articles included unspecified needs in this domain ($n = 3$), but the indicated

Fig. 2. Median prevalence of information needs among relatives by domain. Note: Prevalence rates indicate the extent to which different information needs were reported by relatives. Each study could report met, unmet, and unspecified needs separately, as they correspond to distinct measurements.

prevalence rates were high. There was a high need for information about late effects and follow-up [28,46,54]. Nonetheless, the need for information on follow-up decreased after the end of treatment [54].

Lifestyle. Unspecified information needs in the lifestyle domain were extensive, but only addressed in a few articles ($n = 3$). Transition to adult healthcare and lifestyle behavior had the highest prevalence rates, which decreased over time [54]. Most other lifestyle-related needs increased over time, such as the need for information on patient employment [54].

Family. Unspecified information needs in the family domain were discussed in only two articles and ranged from 39% to 55% [46,54].

Support. Three articles included needs in the support domain. Frequent unspecified information needs were found, especially for psychological and adjustment issues [34,46,54]. Information on financial support was less frequently needed [46].

3.4. Aim 2: factors associated with information needs

The included studies have explored several possible factors associated with information needs of family members. We classified them into three areas: family-, child-, and disease-related characteristics. Several publications found no significant associations and concluded that the assessed information needs were independent of these characteristics [18,29,33,51,53]. Seventeen articles found significant associations between family-, child-, and cancer-related characteristics and unmet, met, or unspecified information needs (Table 4) [11,16,17,23,25,26,32,35,41,42,45,47,49,50,56,58,62].

3.4.1. Family characteristics

The strongest evidence was found for family characteristics. No dissatisfaction with follow-up care [47], having no support person [23], more time spent caring [49], and higher anxiety levels [50] were strongly associated with higher unmet information needs. Satisfaction with information is highest at 10 to 15 years after diagnosis [16]. A larger family size (i.e., in the direct family, meaning more siblings) was strongly associated with lower unmet information needs in one article [49] and associated with higher met information needs in another article [32]. Quality of life was associated with more unmet information needs in one article [35], and fewer in another article [42].

Parents with higher education were more likely to report met information needs, especially for medical information [32]. Having a **migrant** background, not receiving prior health training, and being a paternal grandparent were associated with higher unspecified information needs [16,45].

3.4.2. Child characteristics

Poorer health status of the child was a factor for higher unmet information needs among parents [17]. The child's age was associated with information needs, showing that parents of an older survivor were more likely to report unspecified information needs [41].

3.4.3. Disease characteristics

More medical appointments and bone marrow transplantation or surgery treatment were associated with higher unmet information needs [23,26]. The child being in active treatment compared to completed treatment was associated with higher met information needs among parents [62].

4. Discussion and conclusion

4.1. Discussion

This review provides a thorough overview of the information needs of relatives of childhood cancer patients and survivors. To our knowledge, it is the first systematic review to integrate a heterogeneous sample of different relatives, diagnoses, and stages along the cancer

continuum. Hence, it can help oncology and healthcare professionals better understand information needs in different contexts.

In general, most articles identified information needs in the domain of medical information, with a large number focusing on unmet information needs. Family members reported highest unmet information needs on cancer-related consequences, specifically indicating that they desired further information on late effects. This is especially crucial since information on late effects is helpful for decision-making [64].

We observed the greatest number of met needs in the support domain, reflecting a successful provision of information on where and how to access support. Concerning unspecified information needs, relatives frequently reported a need for information on follow-up services. Information needs to be consistently communicated so that relatives are aware of the changing situation, avoiding the ambiguity that comes with limited updates [65]. A review of qualitative studies identified this information need only in developed countries [13]. It is worthwhile to assess whether relatives in lower-income countries are aware of the possible late effects of cancer and, therefore, develop information needs.

Our results showed that unmet information needs decrease with longer time after diagnosis. This may be explained by lower parental distress after a longer time since diagnosis, adaptation to information-seeking, or distancing from the disease [66]. Likewise, longitudinal studies showed fewer unspecified and unmet needs, and more met needs over time [28,33,54]. Yet, the unspecified or unmet need for information about late effects, patient employment, and health insurance increased, but these are topics that become more prominent at an older age in general.

Kinship may be a determinant of information needs. Overall, the information needs of grandparents and siblings were similar to parents' needs. However, grandparents had a higher unmet need for diagnosis-specific information [16]. This is consistent with previous findings showing that grandparents are excluded from the information loop, leading to frustration, unpreparedness, and isolation [8]. This may be linked to privacy regulations that only allow family members to receive information with permission from the direct caregiver [67].

Siblings occasionally reported lower needs than parents or no unmet needs [31,48]. The lack of some information needs among siblings may be justified by their young age or because they are not directly affected by some issues (e.g., insurance or fertility-related information needs). Other possible reasons for the lack of needs could be concerns about information overload or avoidance behavior because of anxiety [4,65]. Moreover, contrasting results on the role of siblings indicate that further research is needed to determine whether siblings are a burden or a source of support for parents. Long et al. [4] showed a two-step process in which healthy siblings become aware of the impact of cancer on the family and subsequently help the family to function well despite the cancer diagnosis, leading to a sense of family cohesion. In this regard, healthy siblings first need to acquire the right knowledge to enable this supportive family construction, which may be difficult for younger siblings [4].

Two articles on bereaved parents showed fewer unmet information needs compared to relatives at other cancer stages [24,63]. Similarly, relatives of patients desired slightly more medical information than relatives of survivors. Unmet needs did not show a pattern with respect to cancer stage among all domains. There was also no robust evidence of a relationship between needs and country of data collection or type of diagnosis. Nevertheless, having a CNS tumor diagnosis was associated with fewer unmet information needs [17]. CNS tumor survivors are known to have a higher risk of late effects and lower health-related quality of life than survivors of other cancers [68], thus healthcare professionals may already succeed in providing additional information to this group.

The evidence that information needs are associated with anxiety and quality of life confirms the importance of meeting needs [4,6,7,12,65]. Information needs were not homogeneous regarding individuals' characteristics. Parents with a migrant background or without prior health

Table 4
 Characteristics associated with unmet, met, and unspecified information needs.

Area	Associated variables	Unmet needs			Met needs			Unspecified needs		
		Coefficient	p-value	Ref.	Coefficient	p-value	Ref.	Coefficient	p-value	Ref.
Parent	Satisfaction with long-term follow-up care	Neither: OR= 42.64 Satisfied: OR= 4.09	$p = 0.001$	[47]						
	No support person	$\beta = 13.20$	$p < 0.05$	[23]						
	More family members	$\beta = -1.056$	$p < 0.001$	[49]	$t = 6.19$	$p = 0.003$	[32]			
					Physical ¹ :	$p < 0.001$	[32]			
					$t = 9.14$					
					Lifestyle ¹ :	$p < 0.001$	[32]			
					$t = 8.50$					
	Time spent caring	$\beta = 0.615$	$p = 0.018$	[49]						
	Quality of life	$r = -0.587$	$p < 0.001$	[42]						
		$r = 0.457$	$p < 0.001$	[35]						
	Anxiety	$\beta = 0.459$	$p < 0.001$	[50]						
	Made a genetic attribution	OR= 2.81	$p = 0.033$	[47]						
	Education	$\beta = 0.150$	$p < 0.001$	[49]	$t = 8.68$	$p < 0.001$	[58]			
					Medical ¹ :	$p < 0.001$	[58]			
					$t = 16.70$					
				Physical ¹ :	$p < 0.001$	[58]				
				$t = 8.66$						
				Mental ¹ :	$p = 0.027$	[58]				
				$t = 3.69$						
Age	$\beta = 0.118$	$p < 0.001$	[25]				$\beta = -0.05$	$p = 0.016$	[16]	
							Supporting themselves ¹ :	$p = 0.021$	[16]	
							$\beta = -0.04$			
Receiving written information	OR= 0.37	$p < 0.001$	[17]	OR= 3.61	$p < 0.001$	[17]				
Economic status				$t = 4.98$	$p = 0.008$	[32]				
				Medical ¹ :	$p < 0.001$	[32]				
				$t = 9.91$						
				Physical ¹ :	$p = 0.003$	[32]				
				$t = 5.98$						
NCLE information ¹ : perceived NCLE risk				$\beta = -0.29$	$p = 0.007$	[62]				
Perception of child's health				$\beta = 0.26$	-	[62]				
Perceived risk for NCLE				$\beta = -0.17$	-	[62]				
No prior health training							Supporting others ¹ :	$p = 0.021$	[16]	
							$\beta = -1.08$			
							Cancer progression ¹ :	$p = 0.055$	[16]	
							$\beta = -0.81$			
Migrant background							OR= 5.55	$p = 0.039$	[45]	
Paternal grandparents							$\beta = -0.66$	$p = 0.011$	[16]	
							Cancer progression ¹ :	$p = 0.018$	[16]	
							$\beta = -0.58$			
Not receiving all the information							OR= 2.95	$p = 0.035$	[45]	
							Late effects ¹ :	$p = 0.045$	[45]	
							OR= 2.62			
Concerns about consequences of cancer							Medium:	$p = 0.024$	[45]	
							OR= 2.50			
							High: OR= 2.95			
							Illness ¹ :	$p = 0.017$	[45]	
							Medium:			
							OR= 2.42			
							High: OR= 2.84			
							Treatment ¹ :	$p = 0.050$	[45]	
							Medium:			
							OR= 2.04			
							High: OR= 2.47			
							Follow-up ¹ :	$p = 0.008$	[45]	
							Medium:			
							OR= 2.42			
							High: OR= 3.16			
							Late effects ¹ :	$p = 0.019$	[45]	
							Medium:			
							OR= 2.11			
							High: OR= 3.06			
							OR= 2.1	$p = 0.049$	[45]	
Follow-up information: involved in follow-up care ¹										
Information about cancer progression ¹ : preference for amount of information receiving							$\beta = 0.34$	$p = 0.032$	[16]	

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

Area	Associated variables	Unmet needs			Met needs			Unspecified needs			
		Coefficient	p-value	Ref.	Coefficient	p-value	Ref.	Coefficient	p-value	Ref.	
Child	Household income							4-6 million won ³ : OR= 0.46	p = 0.021	[41]	
								≥ 6 million won ³ : OR= 0.52			
	Gender: fathers		p = 0.005	[17]		p = 0.008	[17]	-	p = 0.001	[58]	
	Health status	Moderate disability:		p = 0.039	[17]	OR= 0.37		p = 0.001	[17]		
		Severe disability:		p < 0.001	[17]	OR= 0.34		p < 0.001	[17]		
	Late effects information ¹ : have late effects							OR= 2.95	p = 0.016	[47]	
	Older age							12-19 years:	p = 0.008	[41]	
								OR= 2.62			
								≥ 19 years:	-	[41]	
								OR= 3.18			
Disease	Illness duration: less than 3 years							-	p = 0.01	[11]	
	Time since diagnosis				-		p = 0.025	[17]			
						10-15 years:		p = 0.037	[17]		
								OR= 1.76			
	More medical appointments	Twice per year:	β = 17.0	p = 0.01	[23]						
		Three or more times per year:	β = 12.1	p < 0.05	[23]						
	Type of treatment	Bone marrow transplantation or surgery:	β = 0.397	p < 0.001	[26]						
			β = 0.23	p = 0.036	[62]						
	NCLE information ¹ : chemotherapy therapy stage: induction therapy stage (ref.)			p < 0.05	[56]						
			Induction stage:	35.60 ²	p < 0.01	[56]					
		Consolidation stage:	34.43 ²	p < 0.01	[56]						
		Continuation stage:	29.76 ²	p < 0.01	[56]						
Active treatment Fewer types of treatments Treatment information ¹ : diagnosis					β = 0.43		p < 0.001	[62]			
					β = -0.21		-	[62]			
								CNS tumor:	p = 0.043	[45]	
							OR= 2.88				
							Other tumors:		[45]		
							OR= 1.44				

Note: Classification of information needs as reported in the original articles

¹ Includes an association with information needs in the specific area as indicated.

² Authors' self-developed score with a maximum of 40.

³ Won; currency of South Korea, as used in the original article

Abbreviations: β, Beta; OR, Odds ratio; p, Probability; t, Hypothesis test statistic; NCLE, Neurocognitive late effects; Ref., Reference.

training were more likely to report unspecified needs. Furthermore, higher education may explain fulfillment of information needs, which emphasizes the importance of understanding and processing information [45]. This calls for attention to subgroups of parents with low education and no health training or migrant background.

4.1.1. Limitations and strengths

Our results should be interpreted in the light of some important limitations. First, the overall quality of the included articles was moderate, affecting the confidence in the findings. Hardly any article reported information on sample size calculation, non-participants, confidence intervals, and statistical assumptions. Many publications were evaluated with low or moderate quality due to poor reporting, which was inconclusive about the risk of bias in the article. This may cause a bias in the current review, affecting its objectivity. Second, only a minority of the included publications used a validated assessment tool and most used cross-sectional research designs. Longitudinal research could not only explore causal relationships between information needs and associated factors, but also more thoroughly explore patterns throughout the disease course. We recommend that future research develops a standardized measure for assessing relatives' information needs at different stages of the cancer trajectory and consistently uses

validated scales for such practices. This would enable a standardized measurement of information needs that can validate new insights.

Thirdly, our findings may underrepresent the perspectives of certain groups. Most participants were mothers from Western countries, limiting the generalizability of our results to other kinships and countries. Furthermore, most diagnoses included leukemia, further limiting the generalizability of our results. Leukemia is mostly treated with chemotherapy, which can be easier to inform about compared to a variety of treatments [69,70]. Hence, the (unmet) needs could be underestimated.

Fourth, the included publications showed inconsistent results. The articles showed several different prevalence rates that could not be explained by methodological differences. For example, two articles reported contrasting prevalence rates of unmet needs for medication-related information while being conducted in similar settings (i.e., country, cancer stage, diagnosis, assessment scale) [51,57]. Similarly, Al-Dhawyan et al. [49] associated larger family size with higher unmet information needs among parents, while Motlagh et al. [32] associated it with lower information needs. Particularly information needs about treatment and prognosis are conflicting, perhaps due to the subjective nature of information. Uncertainties in disease progression make prognostic communication difficult for both healthcare providers and

parents [71]. While some relatives find hope in prognosis disclosure, others may feel the opposite, depending on the psychosocial context (e. g., positivity, preparation, information overload) [72,73]. Healthcare professionals need to be aware of these personal preferences to better meet the individual information needs of relatives. This also calls for multicenter communication studies that may explore the variation further, based on geographic and sociodemographic diversity.

Nonetheless, this review has strengths in providing a comprehensive overview of the complex topic of information needs. Our review covers a variety of diagnoses, cancer stages, family members and topics, providing complete information for oncology and healthcare professionals.

4.2. Conclusion

Relatives reported the highest need for information about late effects, follow-up, and disease, highlighting the importance of disease-related information. Assessing personal characteristics such as migrant background, educational level, and child- and disease-related factors is essential to understanding relatives' needs. Identifying and addressing these needs among relatives affected by the disease is essential to ensure equitable access to needed information for all. This approach aims to facilitate informed decision-making and support families' coping mechanisms, ultimately improving overall health outcomes. To achieve this, implementing individualized approaches tailored to personal needs is necessary for practice.

4.3. Practice implications

The large spectrum of information needs in this review highlights the subjective nature of needs and the interplay between the individual and the environment, including personal preferences, family context, and disease constructs [48]. With the proven success of tailored communication tools in health [74], there is a need to develop personalized information resources that assess individual needs of relatives at the beginning of the childhood cancer journey, reassess them throughout, and provide information accordingly. The question of preferred sources, timing and format remains, but a recent review focusing on the qualitative evidence found that these vary between relatives. Qualitative findings may also explain the need for personalized information needs, as they provide a deeper understanding of sociocultural influences [13]. Hence, it is essential to consider findings from both qualitative and quantitative studies.

Furthermore, the provision of information on late effects, follow-up, and illness requires additional attention, as these needs do not decrease over time. Efforts are currently being made to meet these information needs. For example, survivorship passports that summarize survivors' clinical history to increase awareness of late effects and enable follow-up care have been developed and are constantly refined [75]. Building on this, an interactive electronic health (eHealth) tool could be developed to provide timely information on key aspects, considering the personal factors of relatives and prioritizing family characteristics such as socioeconomic background.

It is crucial to acknowledge that this review is based on quantitative research only, where the choice of scales and information topics may have influenced the frequency of certain information needs, potentially leading to an underestimation of other information needs. To illustrate, genetics-related information needs were highly prevalent among

parents in the few articles which addressed them. Meanwhile, medical information and support needs have been addressed by many articles, but their prevalence remains inconsistent and might differ highly between clinics and countries. Therefore, information needs in these domains need to be interpreted with caution and under-researched topics require more attention.

The lack of research on close friends of childhood cancer patients and survivors points to an area for future research. Friends often closely experience the illness of the child and may struggle with information, but more research is needed to explore their needs and role [76]. Similarly, further research should focus on longitudinal, prospective designs that analyze how needs evolve over the course of cancer among different groups of relatives. Additional research is necessary to identify critical time points at which needs are highest and interventions are most needed. Meanwhile, validated measurement tools should be developed and used to ensure accurate and reliable assessments of information needs. In addition, factors associated with information needs require further research to enable healthcare professionals to target at-risk groups.

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Katharina Roser: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **Yara Sievers:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Gisela Michel:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Katrin Scheinemann:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Anica Ilic:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Search strategy

	PubMed	PsycINFO	CINAHL	Scopus
Block 1: Child	child OR child* OR kid* OR baby* OR infant OR infant* OR newborn* OR neonat* OR pediatric* OR paediatric* OR girl* OR boy* OR toddler* OR "pre-schooler" OR preschooler* OR "pre schooler" OR "pre schoolers" OR adolescent OR adolescen* OR young* OR youth* OR teen*	child* OR kid* OR baby* OR infant* OR newborn* OR neonat* OR pediatric* OR paediatric* OR girl* OR boy* OR toddler* OR "pre-schooler" OR preschooler* OR "pre schooler" OR "pre schoolers" OR adolescent health OR adolescen* OR young* OR youth* OR teen*	child OR child* OR kid* OR baby* OR infant OR infant* OR newborn* OR neonat* OR pediatric* OR paediatric* OR girl* OR boy* OR toddler* OR "pre-schooler" OR preschooler* OR "pre schooler" OR "pre schoolers" OR adolescent health OR adolescen* OR young* OR youth* OR teen*	child OR child* OR kid* OR baby* OR infant OR infant* OR newborn* OR neonat* OR pediatric* OR paediatric* OR girl* OR boy* OR toddler* OR {pre-schooler} OR preschooler* OR {pre schooler} OR {pre schoolers} OR adolescent OR adolescen* OR young* OR youth* OR teen*
Block 2: Kinship	grandparents OR grandparent* OR "grand parent" OR "grand parents" OR grandmother* OR "grand mother" OR "grand mothers" OR grandfather* OR "grand father" OR "grand fathers" OR grandchild* OR "grand child" OR "grand children" OR granddaughter* OR "grand daughter" OR "grand daughters" OR grandson* OR "grand son" OR "grand sons" OR parents OR parent* OR mother* OR father* OR daughter* OR son* OR siblings OR sibling* OR brother* OR sister* OR spouses OR spouse* OR partner* OR husband* OR wife* OR wive* OR daughter* OR son* OR caregivers OR caregiver* OR carer* OR "care giver" OR "care givers" OR famil* OR relative* OR friends OR friend* OR "important other" OR "important others" OR "significant other" OR "significant others"	grandparents OR grandparent* OR "grand parent" OR "grand parents" OR grandmother* OR "grand mother" OR "grand mothers" OR grandfather* OR "grand father" OR "grand fathers" OR grandchild* OR "grand child" OR "grand children" OR granddaughter* OR "grand daughter" OR "grand daughters" OR grandson* OR "grand son" OR "grand sons" OR parents OR parent* OR mother* OR father* OR daughter* OR son* OR siblings OR sibling* OR brother* OR sister* OR spouses OR spouse* OR partner* OR husband* OR wife* OR wive* OR daughter* OR son* OR caregivers OR caregiver* OR carer* OR "care giver" OR "care givers" OR famil* OR relative* OR friendship OR friend* OR "important other" OR "important others" OR "significant other" OR "significant others"	grandparents OR grandparent* OR "grand parent" OR "grand parents" OR grandmother* OR "grand mother" OR "grand mothers" OR grandfather* OR "grand father" OR "grand fathers" OR grandchild* OR "grand child" OR "grand children" OR granddaughter* OR "grand daughter" OR "grand daughters" OR grandson* OR "grand son" OR "grand sons" OR parents OR parent* OR mother* OR father* OR daughter* OR son* OR siblings OR sibling* OR brother* OR sister* OR spouses OR spouse* OR partner* OR husband* OR wife* OR wive* OR daughter* OR son* OR caregivers OR caregiver* OR carer* OR "care giver" OR "care givers" OR famil* OR relative* OR friendship OR friend* OR "important other" OR "important others" OR "significant other" OR "significant others"	grandparents OR grandparent* OR {grand parent} OR {grand parents} OR grandmother* OR {grand mother} OR {grand mothers} OR grandfather* OR {grand father} OR {grand fathers} OR grandchild* OR {grand child} OR {grand children} OR granddaughter* OR {grand daughter} OR {grand daughters} OR grandson* OR {grand son} OR {grand sons} OR parent OR parent* OR mother* OR father* OR daughter* OR son* OR siblings OR sibling* OR brother* OR sister* OR spouses OR spouse* OR partner* OR husband* OR wife* OR wive* OR daughter* OR son* OR caregivers OR caregiver* OR carer* OR {care giver} OR {care givers} OR famil* OR relative* OR friend OR friend* OR {important other} OR {important others} OR {significant other} OR {significant others}
Block 3: Information needs	Needs assessment OR "information need" OR "information needs" OR "need for information" OR "need of information" OR "health information" OR "information preference" OR "information preferences" OR "knowledge need" OR "knowledge needs" OR "wish for information" OR "wish of information" OR "desire for information" OR "desire of information" OR "request for information" OR "requests of information" OR "informational need" OR "informational needs" OR "informative need" OR "informative needs"	Needs assessment OR "information need" OR "information needs" OR "need for information" OR "need of information" OR "health information" OR "information preference" OR "information preferences" OR "knowledge need" OR "knowledge needs" OR "wish for information" OR "wish of information" OR "desire for information" OR "desire of information" OR "request for information" OR "requests of information" OR "informational need" OR "informational needs" OR "informative need" OR "informative needs"	Information needs OR "information need" OR "information needs" OR "need for information" OR "need of information" OR "health information" OR "information preference" OR "information preferences" OR "knowledge need" OR "knowledge needs" OR "wish for information" OR "wish of information" OR "desire for information" OR "desire of information" OR "request for information" OR "requests of information" OR "informational need" OR "informational needs" OR "informative need" OR "informative needs"	information demand OR {information need} OR {information needs} OR {need for information} OR {need of information} OR {health information} OR {information preference} OR {information preferences} OR {knowledge need} OR {knowledge needs} OR {wish for information} OR {wish of information} OR {desire for information} OR {desire of information} OR {request for information} OR {requests of information} OR {informational need} OR {informational needs} OR {informative need} OR {informative needs}
Block 4: Disease	neoplasms OR neoplasm* OR cancer* OR malign* OR tumor* OR tumour* OR oncolog* OR carcinoma* OR leukemia* OR leukaemia* OR lymphoma* OR medulloblastoma* OR sarcom* OR radiotherapy OR radiotherap* OR chemoradiotherapy OR chemotherapy, adjuvant OR induction chemotherapy OR consolidation chemotherapy OR maintenance chemotherapy OR chemotherap* OR surgical oncology OR "surgical oncology" OR "curative surgery"	neoplasms OR neoplasm* OR cancer* OR malign* OR tumor* OR tumour* OR oncolog* OR carcinoma* OR leukemia* OR leukaemia* OR lymphoma* OR medulloblastoma* OR sarcom* OR radiology OR radiotherap* OR chemotherapy OR chemotherap* OR "surgical oncology" OR "curative surgery"	neoplasms OR neoplasm* OR cancer* OR malign* OR tumor* OR tumour* OR oncolog* OR carcinoma* OR leukemia* OR leukaemia* OR lymphoma* OR medulloblastoma* OR sarcom* OR radiotherapy OR radiotherap* OR chemoradiotherapy OR chemotherapy, cancer OR chemotherap* OR "surgical oncology" OR "curative surgery"	neoplasms OR neoplasm* OR cancer* OR malign* OR tumor* OR tumour* OR oncolog* OR carcinoma* OR leukemia* OR leukaemia* OR lymphoma* OR medulloblastoma* OR sarcom* OR cancer radiotherapy OR radiotherap* OR chemoradiotherapy OR cancer chemotherapy OR chemotherap* OR cancer surgery OR {surgical oncology} OR {curative surgery}

Appendix B. Prevalence of information need, according to type and domain of information need (%)

Domain of need	Type of need	Unmet needs		Met needs		Unspecified needs	
		Prevalence	Ref.	Prevalence	Ref.	Prevalence	Ref.
Medical information	Health status	Moderate need: 17%	[11]				
		High need: 83%					
	How to prevent a secondary cancer	94%	[58]				
	Treatment the child received	94%	[26]	88%	[52]		
		24%	[63]	M=3.2 ¹	[63]		
		20%	[24]				
	Changes to child's condition	89%	[26]	86%	[26]		
		41%	[63]	M=2.9 ¹	[63]		
	Illness	88%	[59]	74%	[59]	M=5 ²	[34]
		56%	[51]	62%	[49]	Hispanic: 93%	[29]
						Asian/other: 93%	
						Black: 88%	
						White: 88%	
			49%	[45]	Verbal: 91%	[45]	
					Written: 40%		
			47%	[43]	Some need: 48%	[17]	
					Great deal: 24%		
			45%	[31]	60%	[32]	
			12%	[17]	Some: 44%	[17]	
					Great deal: 23%		
			n=1	[57]			
			Some need: 28%	[16]			
			High need: 66%				
			Moderate: 38%	[11]			
			High: 49%				
			M=2.9 ¹	[25]			
			33%	[36]			
	Alternative and natural treatments		87%	[58]			
			22%	[42]			
	When and why changes were being made in my child's treatment plans		87%	[26]	81%	[26]	
		18%	[63]	M=2.8 ¹	[63]		
		51%	[23]				
Spread of disease				Some: 47%	[17]		
				Great deal: 23%			
Genes and cancer		84%	[58]			86%/82% ³	
		31%/44% ³	[47]			[47]	
		7%	[36]				
Tests used to find cancer		82%	[58]				
Cancer genetic risk for other family members		29%/41% ³	[47]				
		Siblings: n=2	[48]				
The chance of surviving cancer		Some need: 10%	[16]				
		High need: 82%					
Treatment benefits		Some need: 29%	[16]	Some: 48%	[17]		
		High need: 63%		A great deal: 25%			
Health opportunities		Moderate: 38%	[11]				
		High: 51%					
Results of medical tests				Some need: 52%	[17]		
				Great deal: 30%			
Purpose of medical tests				Some: 53%	[17]		
				A great deal: 27%			
Procedures of medical tests				Some: 52%	[17]		
				A great deal: 25%			
Cancer treatment		Moderate: 28%	[11]	Verbal: 88%	[45]	88%-75% ⁴	
		High: 70%		Written: 46%		[54]	
		Some need: 32%	[16]	Siblings: 79%	[31]	50% ⁵	
		High need: 62%		Parents: 70%		[46]	
		53%	[55]	Some: 49%	[31]		
		51%-37% ⁴	[54]	A great deal: 31%			
		49%	[45]				
		30%	[31]				
		23% ⁵	[46]				
		18%	[17]				
		13%	[36]				
Secondary cancers		53% ⁵	[46]			79% ⁵	
Relapse		32% ⁵	[46]			85%	
		4%	[17]			[46]	

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(continued)

Domain of need	Type of need	Unmet needs		Met needs		Unspecified needs	
		Prevalence	Ref.	Prevalence	Ref.	Prevalence	Ref.
		Some need: 30%	[16]				
		High need: 60%					
	Health and physical restrictions	47%-10% ⁴	[54]			93%-94% ⁴	[54]
	Chances of treatment success	40%	[55]				
	Effects of cancer on the length of your child's life	40%	[55]				
	Medication	47%	[51]			85%	[51]
		14%	[57]				
		16%	[24]				
	Benefits and side effects of treatment/surgery	47%	[55]				
		41%	[43]				
	How available cancer treatments differ in quality of life	15%	[30]				
	Warning that treatment completion is a difficult time	Mothers: 36%	[48]				
		Fathers: 27%					
		Siblings: 0%					
	Details about the trial	5%	[57]				
	Alternative therapies	Mothers: n=1	[48]				
		Fathers: n=2					
		M=5 ²	[56]				
	Prognosis	93%	[26]	70%	[26]		
		M=5 ²	[56]	Parents: 51%	[31]		
				Siblings: 36%			
		Siblings: 64%	[31]	M=2.7 ¹	[63]		
		Parents: 47%					
		50%	[63]	67%	[36]		
		33%	[36]				
		Some need: 23%	[16]				
		High need: 72%					
		14%	[42]				
		n=1	[57]				
		High: 28%	[11]				
		Moderate: 41%					
	Likelihood of cure	15%	[30]			Black: 92%	[29]
						Asian/other: 92%	
						Hispanic: 89%	
						White: 86%	
						68% ⁵	[46]
	Fatigue	29% ⁵	[46]				
	Survivor physical needs	22%	[42]				
	Pain	19% ⁵	[46]			22% ⁵	[46]
	How to treat emotional symptoms	19%	[30]				
	How to treat pain	9%	[30]				
	How to treat physical symptoms	9%	[30]				
	Non-medical treatments			Some: 31%	[17]		
				A great deal: 12%			
	Effects of treatments on symptoms			Some: 45%	[17]		
				A great deal: 20%			
	Immunization	Fathers: 15%	[48]				
		Mothers: 11%					
		Siblings: 0%					
	Rare cancers	Mothers: 7%	[48]				
		Fathers: 3%					
		Siblings: 0%					
	Causes of illness	6%	[17]	Some: 23%	[17]		
				Great deal: 9%			
	Symptoms of recurrence	Mothers: n=3	[48]				
		Siblings: 7%	[48]				
		Mothers: 5%					
		Fathers: 3%					
Cancer-related consequences	Side effects of treatment	98%	[52]	74%	[26]		
		90%	[26]	M=2.7 ¹	[63]		
		29%	[42]	Some: 34%	[17]		
				A great deal: 17%			
		22%	[63]				
		82%	[58]				
		94%	[26]	60%	[26]		
		33%	[63]	M=2.8 ¹	[63]		
		29%	[24]				
		Follow-up care	57%	[45]	Verbal: 85%	[45]	82% ⁵
				Written: 27%			
		39% ⁵	[46]				
		11%	[17]				

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(continued)

Domain of need	Type of need	Unmet needs		Met needs		Unspecified needs	
		Prevalence	Ref.	Prevalence	Ref.	Prevalence	Ref.
	Schedule of follow-up appointments	49%-13% ⁴	[54]			93%-94% ⁴	[54]
	Review of follow-up tests	49%-17% ⁴	[54]			100%-78% ⁴	[54]
	Aftercare available/needed	33%	[38]				
	What to eat to manage side effects	91%	[58]				
	Things the patient can do to promote well-being			Some: 14%	[17]		
				A great deal: 11%			
	Effects on patient's life			Some: 23%	[17]		
				A great deal: 10%			
	Late effects	91%	[58]	Verbal: 75%	[45]	98%-97% ⁴	[54]
		54%	[46]	Written: 19%			
				Some: 24%	[17]	92%	[28]
				A great deal: 11%			
		71%	[45]			90%	[46]
		53%-40% ⁴	[54]				
		43%	[17]				
	Future limitations in intelligence					82%-92%-94% ⁴	[28]
	Future limitations in physical abilities					89%-92%-93% ⁴	[28]
	Impact on quality of life	28%	[30]	Moderate: 29%	[30]	82%-93%-92% ⁴	[28]
				A lot: 56%			
	How the cancer and its treatment could affect the child's psychological health	Parents: 85%	[31]				
		Siblings: 71%					
	Possible long-term consequences/effects of the cancer	Some need: 15%	[16]				
		High need: 82%					
	Neurocognitive late effects	M=5.2	[62]	M=4 ⁶	[36]		
		To very large extent: 64%					
				100%	[44]		
	How the cancer and its treatment could affect the child's physical health	Siblings: 64%	[31]				
		Parents: 55%					
	Possible difficulties in the child's social behavior	-	[38]				
	Post-cancer fatigue	Mothers: 7%	[48]				
		Fathers: 6%					
		Siblings: 0%					
	Whether a cancer survivor can become an organ donor	Mothers: n=1	[48]				
	Information in later life	3%	[17]				
	Consequences of social life	4%	[17]				
	Other areas/facilities of care			Some: 17%	[17]		
				A great deal: 6%			
	Effects on sexuality			Some: 17%	[17]		
				A great deal: 8%			
	How to find information about the side effects of treatments	55%	[35]				
	Psychological impact of illness/treatment			Moderate: 31%	[30]		
				A lot: 43%			
	Physical consequences of illness/treatment	41%	[43]	Parents: 44%	[31]		
				Siblings: 36%			
				Moderate: 23%	[30]		
				A lot: 70%			
	Impact of cancer and its treatment on daily activities	20%	[30]				
	Chemotherapy side effects			90%	[52]		
	Possible treatment-related cognitive/school problems	48%	[61]	Somewhat: 18%	[44]		
				A lot: 49%			
		56%	[44]	Siblings: 29%	[31]		
				Parents: 14%			
Lifestyle	Healthier ways to eat	88%	[58]				
	Relaxation	86%	[58]				
	Available resources to address learning difficulties	67%	[61]				
	Parent legal rights related to educational access	63%	[61]				
	Need for neuropsychological testing	61% ⁵	[61]				
	Communication with school staff	61%-23% ⁴	[54]			53%-86% ⁴	[54]
	Child's school reentry	51%	[61]				
	Transition to adult healthcare	71%-46% ⁴	[54]				
		40%	[39]				
	Information to help planning child's future	49%	[39]				
	Patient employment	18%-13% ⁴	[54]			27%-64% ⁴	[54]
	Survivor having their own children	45%	[47]				
	Lifestyle	56%-23% ⁴	[54]	50%	[32]		
	Melanoma/skin cancer	52% ⁵	[46]			70% ⁵	[46]
	Managing vitamin D	49% ⁵	[46]			49% ⁵	[46]
	Sun protection	40% ⁵	[46]			63% ⁵	[46]

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Domain of need	Type of need	Unmet needs		Met needs		Unspecified needs	
		Prevalence	Ref.	Prevalence	Ref.	Prevalence	Ref.
Family	Physical activity	35%-0% ⁴	[54]			74%-78% ⁴	[54]
		39% ⁵	[46]			53%	[46]
	Future health behavior	31% ⁵	[46]			42% ⁵	[46]
	How to keep (or get) yourself physically healthy	Some need: 31%	[16]				
		High need: 9%					
	Nutrition	41%	[43]	81%	[27]	55% ⁵	[46]
		38% ⁵	[46]			67%-71% ⁴	[54]
		28%	[54]				
	Lifestyle behavior					84%-78% ⁴	[54]
	Food/drug interactions					58%	[27]
	Food/illness interactions					52%	[27]
	What nutrients should/should not be eaten					46%	[27]
	Mealtime frequency					36%	[27]
	Mealtime					35%	[27]
	Food preparation and cooking					29%	[27]
	Food cleaning					28%	[27]
	Information resources after discharge					n=6	[27]
	Child's diet					23%	[27]
	Food preservation					22%	[27]
	Appetite loss					n=3	[27]
	Compliance to diet					n=5	[27]
	Education advice	30% ⁵	[46]			41% ⁵	[46]
	School	24%-28% ⁴	[54]			59%-22% ⁴	[54]
		5%	[17]				
	Fertility	63%	[46]	10%	[60]	72% ⁵	[46]
		43%	[42]				
		5%	[17]				
		Fathers: 44%	[48]				
		Mothers: 32%					
		Siblings: 0%					
		7%	[36]				
	Sexual issues	49% ⁵	[46]			54% ⁵	[46]
	Contraception	33% ⁵	[46]			33% ⁵	[46]
	Relationship issues	29% ⁵	[46]			29%	[46]
	Advice on issues of social-law	22%	[63]	M=2.7 ¹	[63]		
	Accessing legal services	20%	[42]				
	Religious or spiritual issues	3%	[30]				
	How to handle the feelings of other children	87%	[26]	67%	[26]		
		50%	[63]	M=1.7 ¹	[63]		
		Some need: 37%	[16]				
		High need: 30%					
	How to give information to my other children	84%	[26]	53%	[26]		
		56%	[63]	M=1.8 ¹	[63]		
	What information to give to my other children	81%	[26]	51%	[26]		
		44%	[63]	M=1.8 ¹	[63]		
	Possible parenting difficulties	>50%	[38]				
How to support grandchild's parents	Some need: 37%	[16]					
	High need: 47%						
Support family members	35% ⁵	[46]			39% ⁵	[46]	
Things to do to help your child get well	47%	[55]					
Impact of cancer and its treatment on family life	28%	[30]					
To know that siblings were being well cared	28%	[63]	M=2.3 ¹	[63]			
Ways to maintain a normal lifestyle with the sick child	19%	[24]					
Caring for the child at home	90%	[26]	77%	[26]			
	23.5	[63]	82%	[24]			
	26.7	[55]	M=3.3 ¹	[63]			
	M=4.5 ²	[56]	Some: 31%	[17]			
			A great deal:				
			11%				
Ways to help keep child comfortable	33%	[23]					
Assistance with methods of pain control	28%	[24]					
Home visits by health professionals when needed	22%	[24]					
To have equipment to help manage child's care	17%	[24]					
How to give oral chemotherapy	10%	[24]					
Help in administering medications	24%	[51]	85%	[51]			
Insurance	9%	[24]					
	37%	[42]			54%-55% ⁴	[54]	
	12%-28% ⁴	[54]					
	Fathers: 35%	[48]					
	Mothers: 23%						
	Siblings: 0%						
How to deal with different treatment preferences within the family	22%	[63]					
Types of financial assistance available	17%	[24]					

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Domain of need	Type of need	Unmet needs		Met needs		Unspecified needs	
		Prevalence	Ref.	Prevalence	Ref.	Prevalence	Ref.
Support	Know that I can ask questions any time	90%	[26]	81%	[26]		
		22%	[63]	M=3.1 ¹	[63]		
		19%	[24]				
	Whom to direct questions to	88%	[26]	71%	[26]		
		22%	[63]	M=3 ¹	[63]		
				Parents: 65%	[31]		
	Explanations in understandable terms	86%	[26]	84%	[26]		
		18%	[63]	M=3.1	[63]		
		44%	[24]				
	Feel that healthcare professionals were sincere in caring about my child	86%	[26]	86%	[26]		
		24%	[63]				
		16%	[24]				
	Opportunity to participate equally in child's care	85%	[26]	84%	[26]		
		17%	[50]				
	Trust in healthcare system	89%	[26]	81%	[49]		
		25%	[24]				
		33%	[63]				
	Hope	81%	[26]	71%	[26]		
		17%	[63]				
		16%	[30]				
	Hotlines I can call for information	81%	[58]				
		Advice from others with a similar experience	Some need: 54%	[16]			
	How best to support yourself emotionally	High need: 20%					
		Some need: 53%	[16]				
	Physical care	High need: 16%					
				60%	[32]		
	Mental care			53%	[32]		
		Talking honestly with doctors about your child's future	54%	[23]			
	Vocabulary	52%	[61]				
		Adjustment issues	47%-23% ⁴	[54]			81%-88% ⁴ [54]
	To speak with my child's treating physician at any time	39%	[63]				
		Siblings: 57%	[31]				
	Who to contact with questions about the ill child's care	Parents: 34%					
		Navigating school-support processes	47%	[53]			
	Psychological support	41% ⁵	[46]	Some: 13%	[17]	50% ⁵	[46]
				A great deal: 5%			
	Support services	42%-30% ⁴	[54]			7%-76% ⁴	[54]
		7%	[36]				
		6%	[17]				
		Parents: 55%	[31]	Siblings: 50%	[31]	M=2.3 ²	[34]
		Siblings: 50%		Parents: 44%		16%	[46]
	Special issues if a grandchild dies	39%	[42]				
		16%	[46]				
		Some need: 22%	[16]				
	Where to get help for emotional difficulties	High need: 44%					
Some need: 44%		[16]					
High need: 12%							
Financial support	43%	[42]			56%-77% ⁴	[54]	
	24%-46%	[54]			16%	[46]	
	16%	[46]					
	4%	[17]					
Self-care	36%	[42]					
	17%	[63]					
	5%	[17]					
Palliative care	30%	[24]					
	Some need: 28%	[16]					
To know that child's pain is well adjusted	High need: 26%						
	29%	[63]	M=3.1 ¹	[63]			
Preparation for medical aspects of dying by the team	28%	[63]					
	27%	[55]					
Having oncologist write down all important points	25%	[24]					
	Access to health care professionals' advice outside of regular hours						
Opportunity to say goodbye to my child	24%	[63]					
	To have contact person for every situation at hand	22%	[63]				
Issues other than my child's disease	22%	[63]					
	To be respected for how I deal with the disease	22%	[63]				
To have my child be treated with dignity	19%	[63]					
	To be with my child when he/she dies	18%	[63]				
To reach the team 24 hours a day, 7 days a week	18%	[63]					
	Support groups in your area	13%	[54]				
Reassurance that physical and emotional responses are normal	13%	[55]					
	Communication with primary care provider	11%-23% ⁴	[54]			88%-88% ⁴ [54]	

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Domain of need	Type of need	Unmet needs		Met needs		Unspecified needs	
		Prevalence	Ref.	Prevalence	Ref.	Prevalence	Ref.
	To have enough time to make decisions	11%	[54]				
	To have confidence in the staff caring for my child	11%	[54]				
	Grief or bereavement support					M=2.7 ²	[34]
	Rehabilitation services			Some: 16%	[17]		
	Help outside hospital			A great deal: 6%			
				Some: 17%	[17]		
				A great deal: 5%			
	Other info modes (written/cd)	5%	[17]				
	Support at end of hospital care	2%	[17]				
	Research	2%	[17]				
	Age-appropriate information	1%	[17]				

Note: Classification of information needs as reported in the original articles.

¹ The number indicates a mean on a scale 1-4

² The number indicates a mean on a scale 1-5

³ The prevalence rates are measured in two subgroups of the sample

⁴ The prevalence rates are measured at multiple time points (T1-T2-T3)

⁵ The prevalence rates are interpreted from a graph and may not be completely accurate

⁶ The number indicates a mean on a scale 1-6

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